

Exploring Interactive Representations of Chord
Sequences for Mobile 2D Interfaces
using Harmony Expert Agents

Hazar Emre Tez

MASTER THESIS UPF / 2014

Master in Sound and Music Computing

Master Thesis Supervisor: Sergi Jordà Puig

Department of Information and Communication Technologies

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona

Universitat
Pompeu Fabra
Barcelona

MTG
Music Technology
Group

Abstract

The areas such as physics, music visualization, 2D displays and force-feedback have great potentials for discovering new musical interaction ways. In this research, these fields, which have never been put together before, will be investigated, analyzed and combined to explore new ways of musical interaction for composition on tablets using probabilistic models of tonality. The interface will have inherent music knowledge (expert agents) which will be integrated in order to give intuition about tonal movements via the objects on 2D space. The action of these objects are designed in the light of these diverse areas.

Keywords: 2D GUI, real-time music interaction, chord progressions, probabilistic models

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Dr. Sergi Jordà, Sebastian Mealla, Ángel Faraldo and Ricard Marxer for their inspiration and help during the whole year and the thesis period. I would also like to thank my fellow friends from the master, because I have learned a lot from them and sharing the ideas, discussing over the thesis created a great effect. Lastly, I am very grateful to my family for their support and motivation.

Contents

Abstract	i
List of Figures.....	v
List of Tables	vii
Introduction.....	1
1.1 Motivations.....	1
1.2 GiantSteps Context.....	2
1.3 Initial Goals.....	3
1.4 Structure of the Thesis	4
State of the Art.....	5
2.1 Music, Tonality and Probability.....	5
2.2 Alternate Keyboards – Fixed Spaces for Chords.....	7
2.3 Visualization of Music and Harmony.....	8
2.4 Relevant Fields of Music Interaction.....	11
2.4.1 Mobile 2D Interfaces.....	11
2.4.2 Tangible Interaction.....	15
2.4.3 Virtual Environments.....	15
2.5 Influences	16
2.5.1 Physics.....	16
2.5.2 Atomic Interactions, Force Feedback	17
2.5.3 Boids.....	19

Methodology.....	21
3.1 The Iterative Design Process	21
3.2 Design Considerations under GiantSteps Context	23
3.3 Towards the Initial Design.....	24
3.4 Functional and Technical Choices.....	28
3.5 Iterations, Implementation and Problems	30
3.5.1 Transition Probability Tables	30
3.5.2 Initial Conditions of the Chords in 2D Space: Visuals Physics	32
3.5.3 Interaction and Knowledge	36
Evaluation	39
4.1 Aims of the Experiments	39
4.1 Experiments	40
Results and Discussion.....	43
5.1 Probabilities of the Sequences	43
5.2 User Satisfaction, Center Movement and Probabilities	48
5.2.1 The Best Movement Range for the Center	52
5.2.2 User Satisfaction and the Tonal Areas	54
Conclusions and Future Work	56
6.1 Conclusions.....	56
6.2 Future Work.....	57
References	58
Appendix	

List of Figures

Figure 1. H-Pi Plexus

Figure 2. Microzone U-648

Figure 3. Arc Diagrams

Figure 4. Isochords

Figure 5. Interval spacing in Isochords' Tonnetz grid between root and nearest tone

Figure 6. ImproViz

Figure 7. Key Correlation in the surface of a torus

Figure 8. TENORI-ON

Figure 9. Surface: Example of a trajectory through a surface caused by a touch event, indicating the messages sent and the resulting tree activation states

Figure 10. ToCoPlay: Pressing the container's green button creates a duplicate at a slight offset

Figure 11. Solar

Figure 12. Nodebeat

Figure 13. Daisyphone

Figure 14. Sound Bounce: Throwing a sound

Figure 15. GROPE-III haptic display system in use

Figure 16. FingerFlux provides attraction, repulsion, vibration, and directional haptic feedback on and near surface using electromagnets

Figure 17. Boids: Cohesion – Steer to move toward the average position of local flockmates

Figure 18. Interface quality as a function of the number of design iterations: Measured usability will normally go up for each additional iteration, until the design potentially reaches a point where it plateaus.

Figure 19. Schema of our design process

Figure 20. Prototype figure 1.

Figure 21. Prototype figure 2.

Figure 22. Prototype figure 3.

Figure 23. Prototype figure 4.

Figure 24. Prototype figure 5.

Figure 25. Prototype figure 6.

Figure 26. Prototype figure 7 & 8.

Figure 27. The schema of the whole setup, I/O flow.

Figure 28. Example color distribution.

Figure 29. Chord types and distribution of the directions

Figure 30. C:maj chords with different durations to explain distances between the center and chord objects

Figure 31. The chords in the space while the interface is playing Stevie Wonder's Higher Ground.

Figure 32. Symbolic illustrations of positive and negative potential fields at the center for quantization.

Figure 33. Behringer U-Control UMX49 keyboard and its slider marked with a red ellipse.

Figure 34. Probabilities of the Original Song (*Higher Ground*) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

Figure 35. Probabilities of the Original Song (*Lyin' Eyes*) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

Figure 36. Probabilities of the Original Song (*Something About You*) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

Figure 37. Probabilities of the original songs with the mean and standard deviation of the performance of the participants.

Figure 38. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Higher Ground* run. Participant No.13

Figure 39. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Lyin' Eyes* run. Participant No.12

Figure 40. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Something About You* run. Participant No.15

Figure 41. Case A: The center is not moved. Initial geometry of the space is preserved

Figure 42. Case B: The center is slightly moved just on x-axis. Initial geometry of the space is changed

Figure 43. Case C: The center is moved more than Case B.

List of Tables

Table 1. T. de Clercq and D. Temperley, A Corpus Analysis of Rock Harmony

Table 2. For all participants and three songs, in which area the center is when they like it most and least

Table 3. Table 3. Billboard 36x36 Transition Probability Table

Table 4. Questionnaire results

Table 5. Probabilities of original chord sequence of the chords and the generated ones by participants

Table 6. How many major, minor and dominant chords are played in major, minor and dominant areas, for each participant, for each run?

Chapter 1

Introduction

The natural aspects of physical interaction have been investigated for a long time. The tangible and natural user interfaces indeed carry intuitive elements from our everyday lives, because people know how to grasp, slide, turn and play the objects which possess physicality. Although 2D graphical user interfaces (GUI) became usual domains that we interact everyday thanks to mobile phones and tablets, there will always be undiscovered ways of meaningful musical interactions in these interfaces that use physical metaphors.

A useful combination of the different fields which have never been put together can yield new ways of music creation in these devices. In this thesis, these fields will be explored and tested in order to add new ways to the literature and create expressive music creation models.

1.1 Motivations

Most of the people live in an environment in which music has not a natural everyday role. Instead, it is seen more as an activity, practice or forced event. Indeed, the necessity of the practice of the traditional musical instruments keeps people away from getting fully involved. However, making music is strongly related to the will of creation and it can be created by anybody. Therefore, a design which adopts an “expert agent” is considered in this study. This agent is the musical knowledge behind the interface of the system and it will let everybody to be able to use it, a novice or an expert musician.

Making music using a tablet is a quite usual way of making music nowadays. Sequencer applications, collaborative music games, synthesizer applications or instrument applications are a few examples. However, the most of them does not go

beyond being a few minutes of fun or a simple sound-toy. Therefore, there is a lot to discover and push the state of the art further in order to find useful ways on these 2D spaces. The notions that can show the possible paths can be alternate keyboards, music and information visualization, physics, atomic and molecular interaction, tangible interfaces, interactive displays for music, virtual reality, force-feedback systems etc. When the resulting combination is applied to 2D GUIs, the outcome would be a versatile system.

Obviously, there are many aspects to be explored in the 2D spaces for musical purposes. After setting the above-mentioned notions as the base of this project, the motivation of this study aims to create novel and interactive 2D representations of musical concepts.

The influences of this study come from those diverse areas. As it happens in nature, the frequency of the events can be represented by probabilities. By using this notion, the domain of this study is chosen as musical concepts which have transition probabilities. They are not deterministic, however they are deduced empirically. In this manner, many researchers have applied the same approach in music, such as extracting transition probabilities of chords, phrases, notes or song segments and this study is focused and based on these kind of probabilistic models.

1.2 GiantSteps Context

GiantSteps is a project in which MTG takes part. It is focused more on the development of supportive and inspirational musical expert agents, for melody, harmony, rhythm, structure or style. This research is related to its harmony context.

In this context, some of the properties of these agents are enhancing creativity, covering both off-line and on-line modes and promoting real-time interactions with the user/composer/performer.

GiantSteps aims at empowering all potential musical creators, from professional to casual users including children. Thus, it covers novice users as well. It addresses low cost devices such as tablets and smartphones.

The combination of interaction and musical knowledge is one of the main elements of this project as it is for GiantSteps project. It is about bringing the personal contributions of the user within some musical knowledge constraints.

1.3 Initial Goals

The system is designed to use the probabilistic models of music such as chord transition probabilities, because the chords are one of the higher order musical concepts and they are the tonal frameworks of the music pieces. These probabilistic models are fruitful in terms of being models of different genres or specific artists. Moreover, there is no absolute focus on the chords, but the musical concepts which are tied (or represented) by probabilities. Another instance can be the melodic phrases or sections of a song. Using chords to explore that domain and realize ideas in this system is one of the affordances.

The end system will have underlying harmony knowledge (expert agent) which originates from those models. The interface will never show the most probable next state or warn the user, when a “wrong” progression is performed. However, it will make the user “feel” the tensions between represented musical concepts.

This study is directed towards the aim of obtaining unlimited possibilities of music creation using simple objects in 2D space. To accomplish this, the initial direction can be shown with the properties which are shaped by design decisions and the key concepts of the study:

- Exploring possible intuitive and interactive representations of the higher order musical concepts, which has transition probabilities, on 2D space and provide a meaningful visualization.
- Having a system in which novice users can make music using probabilistic models of tonality so that, they can explore tonal possibilities limited by their creativity.
- Implementing these probabilistic models in a way that they define the actions of the objects in 2D space. Those movements will be defined in the light of the numerous diverse areas.
- From GiantSteps: Granting users means of making music starting from simple chord progression models, in a context of genre or a specific song. For example, the movements of the objects will perform a specific song and the user can deviated from that according to the way he or she interacts.

One of the promises of the system is being mobile, so that users will have a portable music creation platform. Spontaneous musical ideas often emerge in musicians’ minds, but they can be prone to fade out rapidly. With the outcomes of this study, the musicians will also have the record their instant ideas, play with them and create other

ones quickly. Finally, the explored interaction models will be essential for music expression, which is the one of the aims of music technology.

The goal of this research briefly is to gather the ideas from the diverse areas and applying them to control high order musical concepts in order to create a data-driven, transformative, interactive interface in which the users can control the music objects on 2D space to form progressions and arrange temporal structure in desired contexts.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

In Chapter 2, a brief review of probability in tonality takes place. The relation between music and probability is reviewed to form a ground for reasons and ways of implementing such probabilistic models. Alternate keyboards and the aspects of visualization of music and harmony take place in order to explain meaningful ways of representing musical concepts. Related fields of music interaction takes place in order to explain the place of this study in this big area of research. Afterwards, an overview of several diverse areas by which this study has been influenced takes place.

The structure of the thesis continues with Chapter 3 which explains the methodology of the study. The old prototypes, design & technical choices and the iterative design process of the project will be elaborated.

Chapter 4 is devoted to experiments. This chapter shows how we conducted the experiment runs from beginning to the end.

Chapter 5 covers results and discussions. In this chapter, I explain and discuss the results from different perspectives.

Finally, Chapter 6 is a short one about the conclusions possible future studies.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

This project is related to many different areas. Therefore, it is essential to find similar interfaces, search influential ideas, review different designs and present important examples. This chapter serves to this purpose and it is written to give a deeper understanding of the context of this research to the reader.

2.1 Music, Tonality and Probability

Humans can understand and use infinitely many sentences in a language. Even a sentence which has never been heard before can make a complete sense. As linguistic sciences investigate these abilities of humankind, similar studies have also been conducted in music. Although music is a similar domain to the language in several aspects, forming computational methods for modeling the musical grammars is a much more difficult task [1]. The studies are progressing towards making robust, creative, style-independent systems. Rather than the old synthetic models, new analytical models may guide the music generation task in a better and more natural way.

Chords are the essential components of music pieces. Therefore, the exploration of music using chord sequences is a promising way. Chord sequences have grammars of music expression in the tonal context. And they are grasped by people in long time by training. Although music perception is not completely probabilistic in nature and even there are stochastic processes in the human auditory system on neural level, an intuitive explanation of the relation between chords and human perception lies in the statistical information [2]. As we listen to music and analyze it, we get experience from the underlying structures in time.

One type of these probabilistic models are data-driven models which consist simple models of music corpora. The studies on data-driven models can be roughly separated

into two; analysis only and analysis & generation. Both of them consist information which can be used for artistic purposes.

One of the analysis-only studies is The McGill Billboard Project which contains the annotations and audio features corresponding to the first 1000 entries from the random sample of Billboard chart as presented in ISMIR 2011 [2]. A few analysis & generation systems worth mentioning here. Simon et al. [3] present an automatic accompaniment system that learns chord transition models from a small database of songs and allows variation of a heuristically-assigned axis of style (a major/minor factor). Chuan and Chew [4] present a system for learning a style from a small number of examples by using a combination of transition statistics and musical knowledge; they then use this model to generate new accompaniments. Allan and Williams [5] make use of a chord model learned from Bach chorales to provide automatic harmonization of melodies in the style of Bach. Another analysis-only study belongs to Temperley and de Clercq [6]. It has an analysis of rock music corpus. They examined the frequency of different chords and chord transitions in 100 rock songs from Rolling Stone magazine's list of '500 Greatest Songs of All Time'.

In this study, the inherent musical knowledge is derived as models from the above-mentioned studies. They are used in order to define the chord progressions, more specifically the actions of the tonal objects in 2D space. Fred Lerdahl and Ray S. Jackendoff's Generative Theory of Tonal Music (GTTM) [7] is also a useful framework to form meaningful structures, because it provides wide possibilities through a hierarchical system which brings interactivity -of the musical concepts- on the tonal space. It adopts the principles of music composition and performance.

Another process about probabilistic distributions is stochasticity. It covers indeterminacy and chance aspect. It is adopted by early computer musicians such as Xenakis and John Cage.

A Markov Chain is a discrete probability system which is useful in musical applications. In Markov Chains, there are states that possess conditional probabilities. In each state, the transition probabilities of the current state to the others are different. The order of the Markov chain means the number of the previous states that affects the transitions. Using Markov Chains has numerous examples in the probabilistic music models.

There is no consensus about how those transition tables of chords and Markov Chains can be used in music interaction. This immaturity a part of this study and it will be explored though cyclic experimentation and discussion, namely an iterative design process.

2.2 Alternate Keyboards – Fixed Spaces for Chords

Alternate keyboards are valuable examples which show the change of a traditional frame of interaction (between the musician and instrument) to a different one. They provide easiness for several different fingering patterns with different orientations and they open a door towards the exploration of new phrases for musicians.

H-Pi Tonal Plexus is a microtonal keyboard with no fewer than 211 keys per octave [8]. The interesting fact about this keyboard is not just having these properties, but also providing a way to adopt different hand placements to the users. So, it is not just an expressive keyboard, but a new instrument which requests a different training.

Figure 1. H-Pi Plexus

Starrlabs Microzone U-648 is a large array hex keyboard [9]. The keymap is programmable and the keys have black and white colors in a way that the board seems tilted. This creates a different hand eye coordination mapping and produces exciting results for a traditional keyboard player.

Figure 2. Microzone U-648

Seaboard is another keyboard which has several unique features [10]. First of all, the control is continuous along the board. The user can play notes between two consecutive semitones, produce vibratos using the keys and feel the pitch by the tactile feedback. The tactile feedback changes along the axes. It is like a tissue which synthesizes sound, when it is been interacted. The user has more direct -compared to a tone wheel- and intuitive control over the produced sounds.

For this study, the idea of geometrically transforming the control and providing an alternative feel for playing is precious, because it is more than enough to evoke interesting results and expression. Thus, alternate keyboards should be taken into account. Even trying an alternate keyboard for a short period of time can induce new ideas and make one more aware of how a musician uses these spaces of chords. The distribution of the chords that occupy alternative spaces is valuable, however, these spaces are fixed. This study seeks dynamic interaction, therefore alternate keyboards are preliminary examples in the perspective of this thesis.

2.3 Visualization of Music and Harmony

Music visualization and its essential examples are needed to be investigated in order to design meaningful representations of the musical objects in this study. One example of this field is *Hyperscore*. It is a graphical system for intuitive music visualization, composition and editing [11]. It can control low (pitch and dynamics) and high level (form and contour) music features. It can be used without any training, because it gives a feeling like sketching and painting the music. It has well-designed sound to graphics mappings which represent structure of music well, so that harmony and counterpoint can be visualized in a simple way.

Golan Levin's studies are the most notable approaches for my work in this field [12]. He mainly focuses on audiovisual interaction, using music to generate aesthetic or analytic visualizations, using visuals to make music and possible visual aspects of synthesized sounds. His works are valuable, because visualization of synthesized sounds and visual representations of high level musical concepts are valuable for this project. His "Yellowtail" is a spectrogram based audiovisual system in which the user can both compose and make real-time performance. About composition, he states that audiovisual sequencers drastically tighten the iterative property of the musical composition process.

Arc Diagrams is a visualization tool which shows the complex repetitive patterns as string data [13]. It yields interesting solutions with music, but the algorithm is not specifically written for music. It can be used also with text or compiled code.

Figure 3. Arc Diagrams

Isochords is a 2D graphical interface which provides a tonal space [14]. In a triangular isometric grid, the user can visually inspect the transitions between chords. There is a lattice diagram that possess various chord types in 2D space. The connections (edges of triangles) are emphasized, if the two chords are consonant. Important intervals, probable progressions and modulations visually represented in different ways, such as color changes and formation of paths.

Figure 4. Isochords

Figure 5. Interval spacing in Isochords' Tonnetz grid between root and nearest tone

ImproViz represents keys and chords by differently structured circles for each channel in an audio signal [15]. It is made especially for visualizing jazz improvisations and to see the melodic and harmonic patterns. After this example, IanniX worth to mention [16]. It is a graphical open-source sequencer in which users can interact and

Figure 7. Key Correlation in the surface of a torus

Golan Levin states that some software artists do not aim to produce entertaining aesthetic experiences, but instead to obtain analytic insight about the structure of a musical signal in the pursuit of visualizing music. The aim in this study is neither entertaining users, nor approaching to this problem from pure analytical point of view which can deteriorate musical concepts. Instead, the way is to find the most intuitive and dynamically interactive representations using user satisfaction or analytic approaches, and to apply them without limiting the users [12].

2.4 Relevant Fields of Music Interaction

2.4.1 Mobile 2D Interfaces

This section consists examples of studies on the interfaces and related mobile device applications. Interactive displays are significant devices for expressive music and many more purposes. A few interactive displays will be introduced in order to show their relevance. In the design process of this study, these examples and their analysis will be crucial to discard poor methods, to find out what to avoid and what to adopt.

TENORI-ON is a display that interacts with the user visually and sonically [19]. The played notes and sequencer information is presented via meaningful graphical representations on the display. It has 16x16 buttons which makes it a discrete interface. Being hand held, fast responsive LED grid customizability and active visual representation of what is being played makes this interface an examples for this study.

Figure 8. TENORI-ON

Kinetic Particles Synthesizer uses the idea of kinetics of particles as a synthesizer model on 2D space [20]. As the particles move, they produce sounds. The output sounds are relevant to particles' shape, mass, velocity, friction etc. Collisions produce percussive sounds. This system is a good example of simple implementation of 2D physics on touchscreens.

Surface is a multi-touch screen that allows users to navigate their musical ideas on a state-space map [21]. Space mapping presents a musical structure and multi-touch property introduces polyphonic control. It can represent the tonal hierarchies on the surface as a map, so that user “walks” on the map via separated surfaces.

Figure 9. Surface: Example of a trajectory through a surface caused by a touch event, indicating the messages sent and the resulting tree activation states

ToCoPlay is another good example of 2D spaces for music [22]. It serves to both composing and performing needs. The users can design their own music spaces on a 2D surface by finger sketching and collaborate to compose or perform with the objects they select and customize in short time.

Figure 10. ToCoPlay: Pressing the container's green button creates a duplicate at a slight offset

Hexatone™ Pro IDM Rhythm Generator is a rhythm based MIDI sequencer by Amidio Inc [23]. It is performance oriented. Users can alter the sound by using embedded sensor data, i.e. acceleration. It is not like a traditional grid-based sequencer. Users can see the sequencing in a 6 directional honeycomb frame which presents the programmable transition probabilities of samples visually. This alternate visualization and a new sequencing system make Hexatone remarkable.

Interactive Games

Solar is a game in which users control a planet on 2D space [24]. As user moves the planet, it attracts the other masses, take them into its orbit, form a protective environment with them, grow or degenerate, transform and etc. These games are -by definition- only for entertainment. However, they are indeed influential. Some of the ideas can easily be thought as metaphors in tonal space.

Figure 11. Solar

Nodebeat is a musical game. “Generators and Notes make up the two types of nodes [25]. Generators pulse and play Notes within proximity. A Note is played in sequence, based on the distance it is from its connected Generator. Pause nodes to create your own beats or let them roam free to have them generate their own.”

Figure 12. Nodebeat

Daisyphone is designed for remote collaboration and it is aimed create a range of aims: from composition to improvisation [26]. This interface provides instant composition, where the process of composition is a part of performance itself. Its design is focused on supporting HCI rules while supporting affordances of personal devices such as mobile phones, graphical tablets and PDSs. Its GUI allows interaction with looping music, remote collaboration (Real-Time multi-user) and graphical formulation of musical ideas. It is definitely a good example of GUI design (color meanings and spatial metaphor) graphical representation of musical concepts, idea formulation, pattern design and multi-modality for this thesis.

Figure 13. Daisyphone

2.4.2 Tangible Interaction

The tangible user interfaces (TUIs) rely on tangibility and embodied interaction. TUIs represent the physical representations of data as Ullmer and Ishii state and they exploit the possibilities of physical objects and our sensations [27]. The material objects can be physically manipulated -grab, slide, turn, put- and the grouping of these objects affects the upcoming events. The most known example of TUI may be the abacus which is an ancient tangible tool for representing and performing operations of abstract concepts, i.e. numbers. The tangibility is not possible in 2D mobile touchscreens. Therefore, TUIs will not be discussed. Nevertheless, TUI's such as Reactable [28], Block Jam [29], Beatscape [30] and Audiopad [31] are valuable examples in terms of successful mappings of physical manipulation to effective sound control and synthesis. Although, 2D touchscreens do not have physical manipulation, the physical representation of musical objects is a related approach to my study.

2.4.3 Virtual Environments

The virtual reality field suggests a broad and free environment which is limited by human imagination. There are hundreds of virtual reality systems and one branch of this field is evolving towards being mobile. It is defined as “*a medium composed of interactive computer simulations that sense the participant's position and actions, providing*

synthetic feedback to one or more senses, giving the feeling of being immersed or being present in the simulation” [32].

Immersive design of DNA molecules with a Tangible Interface is a virtual reality example for DNA design [33]. They present a tedious work of DNA design integration to a virtual environment for applications in nanotechnology. The tangible hand-held tools were used for interaction. This study is one of the first examples of applications of immersive environments to a scientific design problem, after Project GROPE [34]. And there is no reason to avoid the opposite way: applications of scientific phenomena to immersive environments.

In terms of musical applications, creating a virtual environment of harmony space is not the aim, but the virtual environments can be quite meaningful for presenting a visual sense of tonal relationships.

These areas do not have a direct relation to the harmony spaces or high level concepts such as chords. However, they are indeed quite influential for the objective of exploring interesting music interaction models. Similar to the Project GROPE, we can establish a system which inherently has tonal harmony knowledge, does not give information to the user, but “behaves” naturally, so that the user feels the tonal relationships via the visual interactions.

2.5 Influences

2.5.1 Physics

Physical and molecular interactions are excellent metaphors for the musical concepts. For instance, chords. The molecules accelerate and decelerate by gravitational and frictional forces. They have elasticity which can be represented by the spring-damper systems. The magnets have the attraction and repulsion forces. Atoms have bonding energies and probabilities. And molecules have these interactions plus orientation based possibilities. These interactions function with the natural law, therefore they have scientific definitions and rules. Bringing the law of physics to a 2D surface makes us visualize and feel the musical relationships in intuitive ways. And this information can be used for such harmony spaces for the aim of designing intuitive interactions.

Molecular collision model is a study which speculates on the potential of a limited set of interacting particles to produce interesting temporal structures in a two dimensional world [35]. They are basically objects with long term memories. For instance, people in a public space. The paper formulates a generative system featuring

native internal dynamics which are open to disturbances from unpredictable actions of an external user. It follows the general working hypothesis of much alive research; life-like phenomena. As particles collide, they exchange information and complex behavior emerges spontaneously. In this world, Beyls used a genetic algorithm to maximize the diversity and interactions between the particles. There is no aim for equilibrium in the system and this representation can be extended to a ballistic computing scenario or artificial chemistry.

Sound Bounce project is related to the physical metaphors. As metaphors have a prominent role in HCI, they consider a sound as a physical ball which can bounce, be thrown and caught [36]. Stanford Mobile Phone Orchestra performed with Sound Bounce and they reached to some interesting conclusions. They stated that bouncing a ball may not be expressive, but it is playful. This is an important study, because it poses one of the dangers of metaphors in art: being simplistic, or making more like a game than a musical instrument.

Figure 14. Sound Bounce: Throwing a sound

2.5.2 Atomic Interactions, Force Feedback

The sense of touch can convey detailed information to the users. A simple example can be feeling the road through the drive wheel or doctors' touch examination of tissues and organs. In this context, force feedback gives more "real" feeling to the user, because force feedback systems physically respond to the user input. This response can be modeled, changed or abstracted for different objectives. The force transmits inherent information about the system. And feedback makes the user to control the environment in more natural way. Moreover, an improved sensation generates a rapid learning process, which is proven by the following study.

Project GROPE was a famous research on exploration of molecular dockings [34]. The force feedback system with a display allows users to feel molecular interactions and forces directly. For instance, chemists could construct existing dockings. Amazingly, they

could find new dockings for the drug molecules that were unknown by trial. After tests, chemists reported that they have better understanding of molecular attachments and receptor sites. According to the tests, GROPE is more useful, when the interaction is complex, difficult to visualize. Furthermore, it is an excellent education tool. With all these points, this study directly corresponds to the interactions in tonal spaces that I seek to explore for my study.

Figure 15. GROPE-III haptic display system in use

FingerFlux is a system that generates near-surface haptic feedback on interactive tabletops [37]. The setup includes magnets attached to user's hand and electromagnetic actuation. The key idea is starting interaction before touching, so that the user feels the attraction and repulsion beforehand. This idea sounds quite familiar, when we consider the tonal relationships. Listeners can feel how the tension is evolving and how much sooner the piece is going to reach the climax during listening to the chord sequences, before we hear the peak.

Figure 16. FingerFlux provides attraction, repulsion, vibration, and directional haptic feedback on and near surface using electromagnets

PLANK is a music controller by Bill Verplank, Michael Gurevich and Max Mathews. Bill Verplank showed that active force feedback is an effective way to make new music, because it can be both responsive and assertive [38]. It responds to the user input, objectifies the sound and interaction.

2.5.3 Boids

Natural flocks, swarms, herds, and schools have neighbor-based mechanisms [39]. In these collective behaviors exhibited by animals, such as birds, ants, fishes and grasshoppers, each member of the group interact with the close members, so that the whole group performs its purpose of survival or movement in a non-chaotic manner. Craig Reynolds' Boids is a *distributed behavioral model* in which these mechanisms and close relationships are modeled and can be seen.

Figure 17. Boids: Cohesion – Steer to move toward the average position of local flockmates

A similar phenomenon exists in human auditory system. Cook's works on tonal closure and sense of completion support that the bare intuition which poses more recent events have a greater influence on tonal discrimination and determination than events from the distant past. These influences of recent sonorities were affirmed by the experiments on human echoic memory [40].

Boids model and human auditory system metaphorically consist the same mechanism and this mechanism is quite influential and rich for representations on 2D space. Humans successfully relate the last few seconds (echoic memory and residual pitches) to the present sonorities. Similarly, behaviors of a member of the swarm is dependent on the close member. Thus, this excellent similarity must be taken into account.

2.6 Preliminary Boundaries and Conclusions

Considering the fields and examples in Chapter 2, this study uses them as the sources of ideas for designing dynamic interactions. For example, a direction can be creating new intuitive models using transition tables for determining the attraction, repulsion, friction forces between the objects which represent chords in a 2D space.

To be considered...

There are many crucial notions that need to be considered. First, the input gestures must be defined. I have to consider gestural primitives and type of actions (ergotic) involved in the interaction. Then, the reactions of the interface to the input gestures should be defined. The finalization of the feedback modalities (primary and active feedbacks in the case of my work) also must be done.

Flow, “the state in which people are so involved in an activity that nothing else seems to matter”, as Csikszentmihalyi defines, is one of the aspects that has to be considered, while constructing the above-mentioned building blocks of this project [41]. The outcome should not be very easy to use in order to avoid making the users bored. And it should not be frustratingly hard. There is a delicate balance point, the state of *flow*, which will be investigated during user studies by studying learning curves, training the users or redesigning the system. The outcome will be used to make music. Therefore, the musical events which are created by the users need to be analyzed.

The outcome should not be...

- A game-like outcome should be avoided. It is easy to fall into the pit of entertainment without being aware of. A 2D GUI including the sound modality can easily give a playful feeling, but my aim is to create a musical system for composition and performance. Golan Levin claims that “*with these games, a player cannot perform his/her own music, but passively operates the controllers according to preloaded music*” about the poor game applications which users can create arbitrary sounds [12].
- The outcome will not be a sequencer or have eye-candy graphics.
- It is easy to be seduced by the -pitfall of- *randomness*. The randomness can excite many people. The lack of control may guide designers to add randomness, stochasticity or noise, but I will definitely avoid randomness to have a more “interesting” outcome, unless I can clearly have the reasons for adding it.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This project needs constant review and improvements during its completion process. Therefore, it cannot be accomplished by a waterfall design approach in which the end properties can exactly be set and built by order. In this research, the iterative design process is followed to keep constant feedback and evaluation.

3.1 The Iterative Design Process

Iterative design is the cyclic process of prototyping, implementing, testing, analyzing and refining the system through the final state. In order to properly follow this kind of procedure, first, an initial interface design is made. After having an initial design, the main deficiencies of the interface can easily be seen by using it.

After this first step, main fixes were done. Then, we began to define properties we want to implement and test. These properties come from the hypothesis we produced, when we set our goals and broadly imagine the end interface.

The testing and analyzing periods continue with the implementation phase. In this phase, we try to understand the problems related to the properties we define, how to improve them and how to fix them. Moreover, we discuss on what we can implement, if we discard that hypothesis and what we can put on top of that, if we do not.

The most important principle of the iterative design process is that we are not able to fully understand the system, until we actually build it. Therefore, this process needs to be continued until we - at least - accomplish the initial goals.

As Jakob Nielsen states *in Iterative User-Interface Design* [42], one of the advantages of this design approach is spending less time on documenting and more time on designing. Moreover, he states that, this methodology does not involve blindly

replacing the interface elements with new alternative design ideas, but it involves criticism (analyze) and tests at each iteration.

Figure 18. Interface quality as a function of the number of design iterations: Measured usability will normally go up for each additional iteration, until the design potentially reaches a point where it plateaus [42].

Ideally, the interface is expected to be better after each iteration [42]. However, this is not always true, because some implementations are not applied to improve the system, but to add semi-independent properties. Therefore, the true usability curve is not as smooth as the curve in the Figure 18.

As the Figure 18 implies first few iterations add major gains in usability. After many iterations, there will occur a point of diminishing returns where a very little potential for further improvements is left. However, it is unknown whether there is in fact an upper limit of the usability [42].

Figure 19. Schema of our design process

3.2 Design Considerations under GiantSteps Context

Non-expert users often tend to define musical objectives in terms of known songs. This is not true for expert musicians, because they can define their ideas completely in musical terms. This project is focused on novice users, therefore one of the aims is to be able to represent the songs in the 2D space.

One of the main focuses is related to the struggle between interaction and the musical knowledge that is embedded in the system in the GiantSteps context. The interaction is supplied by the user and the “knowledge” - which is harmony knowledge in this case - is integrated in order to let the user use the source, which are the songs database of the interface. In GiantSteps concepts the relation between interaction and knowledge is metaphorically a clash and it can be illustrated as such:

- The user sees the model as a source (starting point).
- This model can be a song (or fragment) or a set of them.
- The user interacts with the system by “perturbing” it.

- In absence of interaction (perturbation), the model becomes also the outcome. For instance, no interaction means that the output is the initial song.
- The more the user interacts, the more the outcome departs from the source.
- Interaction can thus be seen as the excitation energy/force needed for departing from the equilibrium (i.e. the model as a source) and for accessing a novel target.
- All departures from this equilibrium should still be compliant with the system embedded “knowledge”.

3.3 Towards the Initial Design

After having the state of the art and several influences in our minds, several paper prototypes were produced.

In this prototype, the diatonic chords of major or minor tonality are assigned to a pie-chart scenario. The transition probabilities from the present chord to the other individual chords correspond to proximity of the pieces to the center. The elements have attached springs and magnetic properties, so that they move inwards and outwards as the user make progressions from one chord to another.

Figure 20. Prototype figure 1.

This scenario helps representing the relations among the musical concepts which possess transition probabilities. The dynamic change of the degrees that each division span is informative, however it is very limited about more involved user experience. Moreover, its usability decreases, when there are a lot of divisions, which is necessary to be able to play the songs properly. Therefore, we tried to achieve a more exploreable interface, which looks better than a cake-like interface and makes the user more involved during performance.

Figure 21. Prototype figure 2.

This prototype is designed under the influence of labyrinths. The user finds his/her way through the gaps. The width of the gaps correspond to transition probabilities from the current chord to the other chords. The space visually goes through a constant change like a zoom-in feeling: The circles are getting smaller and smaller according to tempo of the song. If the user does not interact, the chord sequence follows the original song, otherwise, user creates his/her own.

This prototype was better than the previous, in terms of requiring more user interaction and constant change of the escape channels for the next chord. However, it still has this “sound toy” feeling and it is not quite novel design. Furthermore, we need to achieve a system which has a better feedback to the user. This need has brought us to the next one.

Figure 22. Prototype figure 3.

This prototype is focused on the force-feedback ideas. The user explores the chord space through a vibrotactile touch-screen. The current chord is on the circle and other possible chords are placed around that as areas which exert different amount of resistances to the finger of the user. The forces are defined by the transition probabilities which represented by springs attached to the boundaries of these chord territories. If user wants to progress to a chord which has very low transition probability, the friction force is higher and it is hard to reach to the tip of the chord areas due to high spring forces on the walls.

The prototype in Figure 22 involves many of the elements we desire. The feedback is functional and good. It is also multimodal. However, a vibrotactile touchscreen is needed. This is not a quite common device, so it's hard to make and hard to test. We decided that this direction is a little bit out of scope and it is better to use these modalities as metaphors. Thus, we have decided to downgrade the less common properties and more abstract elements of this prototype to a simpler, but more effective one.

In this prototype, the current chords is the main circle and all the other “possible” chords appear & disappear around this chord. The size of the chords give visual feedback about the transition probabilities. User can play any chord: the most probable chord, the next chords according the chord sequence of the song or another chord which he/she finds interesting.

Figure 23. Prototype figure 4.

This prototype represent each musical concept with constant visual feedback. It has the idea of exploring the space from a center and it has the visual feedback as the previous one. The circular objects bring simplicity for interaction and it is more familiar than the abstract shapes for users. Therefore, we decided to use these circular objects. However, as we consider representing songs and using more “physical” elements in the interface, we took a route towards another one.

Figure 24. Prototype figure 5.

This prototype is made around GiantSteps concepts and idea of representing songs in 2D space. The chords of a song are scattered on a 2D space. As the time passes, the chords - which are represented by circles in different sizes - get together. Getting together (touching) will cause that chord to be played in a sequential way in which the sequence will be the whole song itself in the absence of interaction. The end cluster of the chords will be the unique representation of a specific song, so that each different cluster will be another song. If the user interacts, it means the sequence will change and it will lead user to have his/her song, derived from the source.

This prototype was a step forward than the previous one, in terms of involving more novel ideas. However, it lacks the precise control of the chord progressions and it is a kind of black box in which users take actions and see what happens, rather than quickly grasp the system and flow with it.

Figure 25. Prototype figure 6

This prototype is focused on representing chords as circular objects which have physical properties such as magnetism in 2D space. They attract/repulse each other. The size of the circles and their acceleration give visual feedback about transition probabilities. Many different tests have been performed in this prototype.

For instance, moving the center creates a repulsive field which exerts force to the chords that have lower transition probability than a dynamic threshold, which is defined by the speed of the center chord (current chord object). However, it is not useful for representing a song in an intuitive way. The space gets chaotic in time, because the objects accelerate. If we apply a velocity threshold and constantly move the center, all the objects reach to the same velocity, which means losing one of the properties for feedback.

Figure 26. Prototype figure 7 & 8

These two prototypes form our base to put building blocks in order to find the way through the initial goals. They represent the most primitive versions the design that we decided to keep. The center represents the current chord and all the other circles are possible chords to progress. On the top of the previous prototype, the velocities are constant and proportional to the transition probabilities. We added saturation difference on the circles related to the probabilities and extra features to help user understand the space with a few guiding lines.

3.4 Functional and Technical Choices

- For extracting the transition probability tables from McGill Billboard collection [2], we used Python programming language, because Python is quite useful for dealing with string operations. In McGill Billboard collection, there is a log file which includes the chord type, its exact time to start and end for each individual

song. Therefore, all the information exist in order to place all the chords into the bars and measures. Here is an example piece:

```

...
59.676190476      61.314472788749995      Bb:maj
61.314472788749995      62.95275510149999      Bb:maj
62.95275510149999      64.59103741424998      G:min
64.59103741424998      66.22931972699998      G:min
66.229319727       67.86368480649996      Eb:maj
67.86368480649996      69.49804988599992      F:maj
...

```

- For prototyping, Processing programming language is used, because it is open source and powerful. It is easy to use the libraries in order to send and receive OSC and MIDI signals. Moreover, it is based on Java. Java’s powerful sorting algorithms, its speed and ease of compiling applications are its advantages. After writing all the program, I compiled the program as an Android application with all the libraries.
- To produce sound, Pure Data is used. A PD patch receives OSC signals which consist chord data. In PD, OSC signals are converted to MIDI and sent to a DAW (Reaper) to produce high quality instrument sounds with VST instruments.

Figure 27. The schema of the whole setup, I/O flow

3.5 Iterations, Implementation and Problems

3.5.1 Transition Probability Tables

There are two studies that are related to the focus of this project in terms of musical data. Firstly, McGill Billboard Project [2] consists 1000 songs' time dependent chord type information. And Temperley and de Clerque's corpus analysis of rock harmony already provides a probability transition table extracted from 500 rock songs [6].

Temperley and de Clerque's probability transition table is built according to the degrees of the chords. Therefore, there is no consideration of tonality or modality. This has one remarkable advantage and one significant disadvantage. The advantage is that it can be used in any key, or tonality, because only the degrees matter. However, there is a significant amount of data reduction. Suppose the song is in Cmaj and it progressed to Emin. This counts as a +1 for this type of progression. If the song is in Cmin and progressed to Emaj (which is the same degree relationship: major 3rd leap), this counts as the same type of progression, although the chords are completely different. Therefore, this table is useful in the cases where degrees are more considerable.

	I	bII	II	bIII	III	IV	#IV	V	bVI	VI	bVII	VII
I	0	0.0085	0.0447	0.0319	0.0149	0.3565	0.0007	0.2406	0.0352	0.1023	0.1593	0.0054
bII	0.6889	0	0	0	0.0444	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2667
II	0.3614	0.003	0	0.006	0.0602	0.1747	0	0.2922	0	0.0723	0.0301	0
bIII	0.2101	0.0252	0.0252	0	0	0.2689	0.0084	0.0084	0.2815	0	0.1723	0
III	0.0265	0	0.0646	0	0	0.7881	0	0.0099	0	0.0993	0.005	0.0066
IV	0.556	0.0067	0.0144	0.0469	0.0215	0	0.0019	0.2459	0.0273	0.0344	0.0431	0.0019
#IV	0.3043	0	0	0.2609	0	0.4348	0	0	0	0	0	0
V	0.5296	0	0.0242	0.004	0.0114	0.2634	0.0027	0	0.004	0.1284	0.0323	0
bVI	0.5668	0	0.0027	0.0545	0	0.0599	0.0163	0.0599	0	0.0272	0.2125	0
VI	0.2146	0	0.1297	0	0.0477	0.3875	0	0.1848	0.0313	0	0.0045	0
bVII	0.5252	0	0	0.015	0.0027	0.2558	0.0027	0.0354	0.1551	0.0082	0	0
VII	0.4865	0	0	0	0.3243	0	0.1081	0	0	0.0811	0	0

Table 1. T. de Clercq and D. Temperley, A corpus analysis of rock harmony [6].

McGill's Billboard Project [2] is richer in terms of number of the songs and user preference, because there is no pre-made transition table. They supply time dependent chord information of the songs in the database. The information is quite precise. They include less frequent types such as augmented, diminished and suspended, so that, it is

possible to use them as it is or just reduce them to major/minor tonality. They supply five different types of chord information files. The exact chords as played in the song, the version reduced to major and minor chords, the version reduced to major, minor and dominant chords, the version reduced to major and minor chords including inversions, and finally the version reduced to major, minor and dominant chords including inversions.

This database is more useful for our project, for several reasons. First, they supply the chords. That's why, I did not deal with finding the right chords for the songs. Second, its precise in terms of time based data, so that we know exactly which chord is played and when. Third, different transition probability tables can be extracted according to the needs, as we did. Moreover, there are more songs than Temperley and de Clerque's corpus analysis of rock harmony [6]. And we can include or exclude the probability of continuing to play the same chord.

From McGill database, we only used the songs which have major, minor or dominant 7th chords. Thus, currently we are not using the whole database. This can be done without a great effort, after desired interaction and initial goals are achieved.

The current transition table we use and experiment is 36x36, which has transition probability from and major, minor or dominant (3 types) chord in any tone (12 tones) to another one. This table is provided in the Appendix.

The problems we faced during implementations were several. First of all, there are zero probabilities in tables. This means that type of transition does not exist in any of the songs in that database. When the user interacts, those types of transitions may be possible. Currently, the solution for this is to leave the system as it is and assign their physical properties according to zero probabilities.

As we use 36x36 transition table, currently we do not consider other types chords than major, minor and dominant 7th. However, it can be changed, as I mentioned above.

Staying at one chords was another issue, because in these databases there is no consideration of probability of staying at one chord, but only changes. Therefore, we accepted that the same chord is played again, if it is the same in the next measure according to tempo of the song.

3.5.2 Initial Conditions of the Chords in 2D Space: Visuals Physics

After going through several prototypes and reviewing visualization studies, we decided how to represent the chords and it is important to make these choices clear.

We decided to represent the chords as circular objects. The objects will have same sizes, but different colors. The hue space is divided into 12, so that 12 tones (C to B) will have different colors. This will make user relate the colors and sounds, so that multimodal feedback will hopefully make users internalize which objects sound how, after a while. The saturation of the objects differ according to their transition probabilities. For instance, if a chord has high probability to resolve to the chord which was just played, its color will be brighter.

Figure 28. Example color distribution

The placement of the chords is not determined according to the cycle of fifths (as in the Figure 28), instead the number of the different types of chords. There are three types of chords that we implemented; major, minor and dominant chords. The reason why only these three types are used is that the most of the songs can be played with only these types. Since, the focus of this project is not making a song player, but creating a novel interface with new ideas, major, minor and dominant chords are suffice.

These three types of chords are mapped to the 2D space as different divisions. For instance suppose, there is a song which consists all these three types. Major chords are placed in the region of -60° to $+60^\circ$, minors are placed in the region of $+60^\circ$ to 180° , and the dominants are placed in the region of 180° to -60° . Among these regions, there are other divisions. These equally divided spaces will again be divided to the number of chords that belong to the individual areas. Suppose there are 3 different major chords in this song, these major chords will be placed with equal degrees amongst each other. In

Figure 29, an example of this distribution can be seen with 2 major, 1 minor and 3 dominant chords. This figure is presented only to show the directions, so the distances to the center can be omitted for this figure.

Figure 29. Chord types and distribution of the directions

If there are two different types of chords (i.e. major and minor), the 360° is divided into two sections and the inner divisions follow the same logic as told above. The reasons of these choices come from interaction considerations. It is much better than placing all the chords by dividing the 360° into 36 and place same type of chord to the same degree for different songs, because our placement offers more even distribution. The main reason is there are different number of major, minor and dominant chords in each song. The color distributions and the separated divisions for 3 different types of chords remain same. Thus, we expect users to get used to the areas of tonality and interact as they wish.

As it is mentioned before, if the user does not perturb, it can play the chords in any sequence, so that it will be the song itself (the source). In the beginning of the performance, all the chords that exist in the song are placed in the 2D space according to the rules mentioned above. The distances are also put accordingly, so that each chord

will sound at the exact time as it is in the original song. For instance, suppose there is a song which consist of only eight Cmaj chords in four measures, as in the Figure 30.

Figure 30. Cmaj chords with different durations to explain distances between the center and chord objects

Suppose the first Cmaj is at the distance d to the center. Since all of the chords are Cmaj, all of the progressions are from Cmaj to Cmaj. Therefore, their velocities will be the same, because the transition probabilities are the same. So, the distances from the first to the eighth is going to be such: d

$$d, 2d, 2.5d, 3d, 3.25d, 3.5d, 3.75d, 4d$$

Consequently, they are going to be played exactly at the right times according to the original song in the absence of disturbance (interaction). When there are different types of chords, their distances are assigned according to the transition probabilities and the number of beats left at $t = 0$. The formula to determine distances is simply this:

$$d_{chord} = P_{transition} \cdot n_{beats\ to\ play} \cdot k_{velocity} \cdot \frac{f^2}{bpm} + \frac{r_{center} + r_{chord}}{2}$$

$P_{transition}$: transition probability from that chord to the next

$n_{beats\ to\ play}$: number of beats to wait to play that chord

$k_{velocity}$: velocity factor to make chords move with a proper velocity1

f : frame rate of the program

bpm : tempo of the song

r_o : radius of the object o

Here is how it looks, when it is zoomed out just after the movements begin for a song in Figure 31.

Figure 31. The chords in the space while the interface is playing Stevie Wonder's Higher Ground.

The particles have radial velocities (constant) towards the center. The particles that reach to the center are “absorbed” (and sound). When a chord is played, the next chord on the way always has the transition probability from itself to the next chord. The velocities are initialized at the beginning.

To define the physics of the system, we tried several scenarios including acceleration, constant and circular velocity. Finally, we have chosen constant velocity, because of several reasons.

- Problem of representing a song by putting all the chords on the space:
If we assign acceleration to the objects, their velocity increases in time and they become hard to control, because of the excessive velocities. The difference between the velocities of different objects become unnoticeable, so that the visual feedback about their transition probability is lost.
- Visual ambiguity:
A faster object has higher transition probability to the current (chord at the center) chord. This introduces visual consistency. In order to keep this, we have

chosen constant velocity. In the case of acceleration, this is the same, however it can be noticed, only if there are a few objects (a song consists of a few chords). If there are more than 50 objects moving towards the center from different directions, there is a high level of visual ambiguity, so that it looks chaotic.

- Easier to control the objects:

When the objects have constant speed, it is easy to hold and drag them.

Otherwise, they keep accelerating and they become harder and harder to hold (to drag) in the 2D screen.

After explaining the initial conditions, the ground rules and the reasons for all of them, it is important to explain how the users will interact with the interface.

3.5.3 Interaction and Knowledge

So far, the initial conditions of the space is explained. Now, it is necessary to explain the system's behavior about the struggle between interaction and knowledge and how it behaves, when the user interacts.

- The user can only move the center, not the chord objects. This creates an effect like the user explores the 2D space with a single object. He/she travels in the space between and through the chords, plays them, avoids them and creates his/her own piece. Basically, holding the center and dragging it to different directions, shifts all the chords in the space. This effect visually seems like the user finds its way with the center, like using a compass.
- Holding/dragging the center stops all the moving chords, so that the chord objects do not move while center is moved. The reason for this is we assume the user do not want to play, while he/she moves the center. However, the user is able to play a steady chord by pulling the center on the chord he/she wants to play, while moving the center.
- When the center is released, after dragging, all the velocities are updated based on the list of the order of the chords. This list of order is created according to the sorted list of times of the chords to arrive to the center.
- All of the chord objects have a field (instance) which carries the information of the number of beats it has to be played according to the original song. When user interacts, this information also preserved to keep the song feeling. As mentioned in the previous point, after user drags the center, the first element of the sorted list is the first one to be played, since it is the closest one in time scale. Right after dragging, the program uses this instance and determine the velocity of the object to make it reach to the center, after waiting correct number

of beats. This process has been applied to all of the chords in the space, so all the velocities are updated right after release of the center.

- For quantization of the sounds in time, all the chords are placed accordingly in the beginning, so that they reach to the center at the correct time. However, user can change the relative locations by dragging the center, so the initial quantization calculations become invalid. To deal with this, first, we applied a small potential field. If an object is close, and the next beat is also quite soon, the center will apply a positive potential field which will accelerate the chord towards the center in order to play it right on the beat. Otherwise, if the next beat is far more than the half beat duration, the center will apply a negative potential field to apply a negative acceleration in order to play it right on time at the next beat.

Figure 32. Symbolic illustrations of positive and negative potential fields at the center for quantization.

However, this approach caused too much accumulation around the center. This is visually crowded and also dangerous in terms of playing the chords. The reason is that, if the user drags the center very fast, the system plays all the chords which the center clashes with.

Therefore, we used another approach: When the center is moved to somewhere else, all the objects velocities are updated according to above-mentioned process. The velocity of each individual chord is assigned according to its order in the sorted time information array and the number of the beats that chord has to be played. When we do in this way, all the velocities are also assigned so that quantization is perfectly preserved throughout the performance.

- The songs end when all of the chords in the space are played. The number of the chords in the space does not change. It only changes, when user picks a different song to perform. The chord dictionary is not mutable. It is limited to the chords of the song user chooses. Thus, the length of the performances depend on the song

and the user interaction. Since, the users can avoid playing any chord anytime, they can make it longer.

Chapter 4

Evaluation

Designing such an interface and testing it is not just about accomplishing a series of tasks, but it is more about understanding what users experience. There are many parameters which have been tried to measure by the researchers about such interfaces, such as usability, expressivity, repeatability, playability, usefulness etc. However, in several recent studies, researchers design unique experimental setups, come up with alternatives to those classic parameters and they evaluate the interfaces in different ways. The examples include longitudinal evaluation approach in which Gelineck and Serafin evaluate playability, explorability and connectivity [43], believability [44], the Repertory Grid Technique [45], the Semantic Differential [46], Structured hierarchical interviewing for requirement analysis [47], the Sensual Evaluation Instrument (SEI) [48], and AMUSE [49].

4.1 Aims of the Experiments

These kind of experimental musical interfaces brings the possibility of being some kind of black box by design. However, all the properties of the system were designed in order to bring the user interaction and pure musical data together in a non-manipulated way. We did not add a property which could change the fate of the progressions directly. The important factors are always the user's actions on the center object and the system's expert agent.

After having the state of art, narrowing down the design and being reached at the end of the iterative design process, the outcomes that we are interested in were clear. We asked questions such as; what the relation between users' joy and level of interaction is, what the conditions that tend to produce the cases that people like are, what the effect of the center movement and its relation with the divergence from the original

model are, what the best range of center movement to satisfy the user is. We are interested in learning how much creative users feel while performing with the interface. We are interested in learning the dependencies between users' joy, progressions they hear and their interaction.

Since the users interact with the interface by controlling a center, move in the 2D space through tonal areas and generate new sequences, here are the things to be investigated:

- Cumulative probability of the original songs individually.
- The likelihood of the whole sequences that users have created for each song.
- Movement of the center (differential and non-differential). The tonal areas that the center is being hold on. The relation between user interaction and deviation from the model (original song itself).
- The types of chords played in the different types of tonal areas.

Our expectation is that the movement of the center has a cumulative effect, in short terms, it creates deviations but the effect will be bigger and bigger in time. Moreover, the more users interact, further they diverge from the original (more novel outcomes) and they will like it. Level of likelihood of the generated product is not expected to be related to the activity.

4.1 Experiments

In order to evaluate the interface, I designed an experimental setup. There are two divisions of the experiment; - as they are complementary to each other - collecting qualitative data and collecting quantitative data. The qualitative data is gathered through two questionnaires and quantitative data is gathered while subjects use the system.

I made two preliminary pilot experiments. In these experiments, I invited two people from my family and applied all the procedures that I designed for the experiment. I let them use the system again and again for two days, asked questions about deficiencies. They commented that they do not want to play the same song

After the preliminary pilot experiments, I started running experiments. Here are the steps of the experiments:

- I tell the participant what is this system about: Brief info about its design considerations, movements of the objects, placements of the objects, what can they do with it.

- Users fill the initial questionnaire to give very brief information about themselves.
- I requested them to listen three songs which are chosen by me from the Billboard database [2]. They are *Higher Ground* – Stevie Wonder, *Lyin’ Eyes* – Eagles and *Something About You* – Level 42. These three songs are carefully chosen. Two of them consist of two types of chords and the other consists of three. *Higher Ground* includes major and dominant chords, *Lyin’ Eyes* includes major, minor and dominant chords, *Something About You* includes major and minor chords. Their genres are soul, soft rock and pop rock respectively, so the variation in genre is achieved. In terms of the balance of the number of different types of chords (major/minor/dominant), they are fulfilling. I asked them to focus on the chords, while listening.
- I made them watch a short video of the interface in action, in order to make sure there are no confusions and something not clear.
- They use the system with those three songs. Generated sequences, timings, the movement of the center in the 2D space etc. I also let them “think aloud”, while they use it. During these runs, the system writes everything into log files.
- They fill the second questionnaire which is to get feedback about their thoughts about the system. The initial and final questionnaires presented in the Appendix with the answers of the users.
- Lastly, I had short conversations about the system; what they liked, what was interesting, what was boring etc.

No matter how much a system is usable and intuitive, it may fail, if it does not motivate the user. We are interested in the moments that they enjoy and they do not. Therefore, I used a MIDI slider to record the level of satisfaction/joy from the users. This is slider of a Behringer U-Control UMx49 keyboard.

Figure 33. Behringer U-Control UMx49 keyboard and its slider marked with a red ellipse

Since its output is MIDI, the range is from 0 to 127. I subtracted 63 from the range and accepted the 0 as the neutral, 64 as the maximum satisfaction and -63 as the

maximum dislike point. The users asked to constantly indicate their feeling about the music they make with the interface. This MIDI data is recorded to the same log files that the interface writes in synch with the performances.

14 participants attended and completed the experiments. Their ages vary from 17 to 62. However, the most of them are between 20 and 30 years old.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, I presented the answers I have found and then discussed about them. As I mentioned in Chapter 3, we are interested the probabilities of the musical pieces that users create, the relation between users' joy and level of interaction, the conditions that tend to produce the cases that people like, the effect of the center movement and its relation to the divergence from the original model and the best range of center movement to satisfy the user etc.

First, I discuss about the probabilities of the original songs and the probabilities of the generated sequences by users. Then, I present the outcomes about the relation between the user satisfaction levels and the center movement. Afterwards, I discuss about the best range of center movement. Finally, I present the relation between the center movement and the tonal areas.

5.1 Probabilities of the Sequences

Since each progression has a probability in this system, any chord sequence with the length greater than one has a likelihood. Thus, the probabilities of the chord sequences of the original songs and the generated sequences (outcomes of the performances) can be calculated. These numbers indicate the likelihood of having a specific sequence among all the possible sequences which consist the same number of chords.

In this section, I calculate the cumulative probabilities for and chord sequence. This means taking the scalar product of each probability of the successive chord transitions for a whole sequence.

$$P_{sequence} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} ChordTransitionMatrix(C_k, C_{k+1})$$

Here, the *ChordTransitionMatrix* is 36x36 matrix which includes the transition probabilities from one chord to another. n is the number of the chords in the sequence. The original (cumulative) probability for *Higher Ground* is 9.31×10^{-202} , for *Lyin' Eyes* is 3.84×10^{-119} and for *Something About You* is 9.38×10^{-159} .

There are a few notions to discuss here. First of all, this simple formula does not take care of the length of the sequence. Hence, the probabilities greatly vary. It seems like, any pair of sequences with different lengths cannot be compared, because there is no normalization. However, the information that we are interested in is to compare the sequences among themselves. We want to see the difference between the sequences with the same chord dictionary. We want to investigate how much the probabilities vary compared to the source, therefore this approach is acceptable. In order to have a deeper analysis and more information about new sequences, a useful normalization should be applied, but there is no generation of new sequences without having a source (a song) in this project. This addition is one of the future works to be done for this project.

Second, the chord dictionaries are exactly the same for all the runs that have been performed for the same song. As explained in Chapter 3, in the absence of user interaction, the outcome becomes the source itself. Hence, the user only changes, alters the chord sequences. He/she does not introduce new types of chords or make more progression than the number of the progressions in the original song. This makes the above-mentioned approach valid.

In the following figures (34, 35 and 36), I present the probability comparison for each song, which consists of the song itself and 14 runs performed by the participants. Those red lines in the following figures are $y = 0$ lines, because these probabilities are calculated by subtracting the logarithm of the probability of the original song from the generated ones. Therefore, the original songs are shown like that. Any sequence which is more likely to be created (compared to the original song's chord sequence) is going to be bigger than zero and any sequence which is less likely to be created is going to be smaller than zero. The blue bars show the probabilities of the sequences that were produced by the users. The y-axes are absolute log values.

The formula is simply this:

$$* P_{sequence} = \log(P_{sequence}) - \log(P_{originalSong})$$

Figure 34. Probabilities of the Original Song (Higher Ground) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

In the Figure 34, it's seen that the most of the probabilities of the generated sequences are lower compared to the source.

Figure 35. Probabilities of the Original Song (Lyn' Eyes) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

Figure 36. Probabilities of the Original Song (Something About You) and the Generated Sequences of Subjects (performances).

These numbers show that this data-driven system does provide a mechanism to promote likely sequences. For each song, the more and less likely sequences change. In *Higher Ground*, the most probable progression is Eb:7 to Eb:7, which is staying at Eb:7 chord. And the least probable one is Ab:maj to Bb:7. This makes sense, because Bb:7 is not even the secondary dominant. Tonally, it does not make much sense. In *Lyin' Eyes*, the most probable progressions are C:maj to C:maj and G:maj to G:maj. So, again the most probable progression is staying at the same type of chord. The least probable one is C:7 to A:min, which corresponds to V-iii motion in F:maj scale. This is not a useless progression at all, but it is apparently not frequent in this database. Likewise, the most probable progression is E:maj to E:maj in *Something About You*. And the least probable one is D:maj to C:maj.

When we investigate the graphs, we see that the trends change for the same individual users. The users also do not perform in a way that they keep their trend in the probability measure. For instance, the participant no.1 creates a quite high

(relatively) sequence in Higher Ground run, then creates a quite low for the Lyin' Eyes, and finally creates the sequence with the highest probability measure.

A few points can be deduced from this. First, it may mean that the more probable chord progressions are not perceived well and distinguished as “tonally common” progressions by the participants. Secondly, it may mean that there is no big reason to bring forward that the users like and try to achieve these “tonally common” movements such as I-V-I. They also may try to hear less common progressions to hear some different or “weird” sequences just to experiment in this experimental interface. Finally, it may mean that “tonally common” progressions do not always correspond to the high levels of likelihood in the embedded knowledge. For instance II-V-I progression is one of the most known and used ones, however, the transition probability tables are created from a limited database. This database may be biased for some kind of progressions and may reflect low values for common progressions as well.

Figure 37. Probabilities of the original songs with the mean and standard deviation of the performance of the participants.

One important fact about this system is that there is some kind of data reduction which cannot be neglected. The transition table we use is extracted from a large database, there are many different types of progressions in the song database. Moreover, this is not a perfect or accurate model of tonal functions. The some of the most known

type of progressions, such as II-V or V-I may not be quite frequent depending on the songs of the database. Likewise, some of the less common progression might be more emphasized, because that type of progression may be in favor for a common genre in the database.

The Figure 37 shows the mean probabilities of the user runs relative to the probabilities of the original songs. The probability of the songs are normalized to 1 and indicated as the green horizontal line in order to present a summarization of the Figures 34, 35 and 36. Furthermore, it is a broad comparison between the different songs. As it can be seen, the standard deviation is the biggest at the *Higher Ground*. As the standard deviations get smaller towards the last song (*Something About You* is the last song in the order of the experiment runs), the means increase. This may mean that the users do less experimental movements and focus more on the progressions with high probability. However, three point data is not enough to claim that, because there is no statistical significance.

5.2 User Satisfaction, Center Movement and Probabilities

All the participants used the interface three times with different songs. While they use it, I recorded a log file. Here, I investigate the relation between the movement of the center (not absolute), user satisfaction, probabilities (4 bar sliding window on third row and 1st order on fourth row) and chord sequences. For the probability plots on the 3rd rows, I took five chords (four progressions) and calculate the probability, then shift one chord and calculate the probability for the next four progressions. For the probability subplots on the 4th row, I just take 1st order transitions, which is one progression per sample. On the satisfaction plot, the color differences indicate in which area the center is.

The figure-specific comments are at the bottom of the figures. The general comments and outcomes, which are deduced using qualitative and quantitative data, are after the figures.

I chose one performance for each song. These three are selected, because they are quite suitable to explain the results I deduce. They belong to different users, so they also vary about the performance and user properties.

Figure 38. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Higher Ground* run. Participant No.13

In Figure 34, minimum user satisfaction level starts at 1.01' and maximum starts at 2.08'. The windows probability peaks can be seen around those points. Many of the probability peaks occur, when there are repetitions of the chords. The reason is the most abundant chords are usually the key chord of the song, which is Eb:7 in *Higher Ground*. According to Billboard database and the transition probability table, the probability of the tonic chord to remain on the next progression is 0.45183. The probability of the vast majority of the other types of progressions are much smaller than this value. Therefore, if the song remains at the same chord for a while, there is a raise in the probability parameter. However, according to interviews and gathered data, they do not like the same chord to be played over and over, that's why the satisfaction level drops.

Figure 39. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Lyin' Eyes* run. Participant No.12

The users like it more, when they hear altered version of the original progression or something not very repetitive. If the chords change, not in a random manner, but rather like changing the places of them in different measure, they tend to like it. This is seen in most of the runs and also several users commented on this. For instance, the chord progression in the region that user likes is:

Eb:7 Ab:maj Eb:7 Gb:maj || Eb:7 Ab:7 F:7 Ab:maj

In Figure 35, the maximum user satisfaction level occurs at 1.4⁷. And the progression is such: C:maj | G:maj | C:maj | G:maj | A:min | G:maj | C:maj | G:maj (in key of G:maj)

The original progression:

G:maj | C:maj | A:min | D:7 | G:maj | C:maj | A:min | G:maj

Figure 40. Distance of the center, satisfaction and Probabilities. *Something About You* run. Participant No.15

As mentioned above, the low satisfaction levels occurs, where several repetitions of chords are seen. Therefore, probability peaks are related to low satisfaction levels. However, here time is an important issue to discuss. To adjust the satisfaction levels, hearing → understanding (cognition) → judgement → decision (whether to change and how much) process takes place. Therefore, the user increases the level, after hearing sequences he/she likes. In the Figure 36, the minimum satisfaction level occurs at 2.7' and we see probability high until 2.7'. There are eight E:maj chords before point 2.7'. So, the user hears this, does not like and decreases the level.

The amount of center movement is not closely related to user satisfaction. The users often started moving it right away. When they did not do it, they still indicate their level satisfaction. For instance, they do not move the center, but they do not like the chords or just the sounds they hear. Moreover, they tend to get satisfied less, when they do not move the center. However, the user satisfaction also sometimes drop, when they move too much or too further away from where they start. One of the reasons of this is the initial geometric definition of the space, when all the chords move to the point $(0,0)$ (center's initial position). When the user disturb the center position – hence the sequences – he/she gets closer to some type of chords and moves further away from some others. If the movement is too much, the user is likely to hear one or two types of chords too much for a while, until he/she plays most of them. Then, the other types of chords, which were far at the beginning, start to dominate. This creates too many same type of progressions and makes the joy level drop.

5.2.1 The Best Movement Range for the Center

The answer of the question “is there a best range of center movement to maximize the user satisfaction” is yes, yet could not be specifically determined. Three artificial cases with just 12 chords, (3 different types) in 3 measures are created to elaborate on this subject. When the center is not moved, the original sequence is preserved (Figure 37, Case A). The user hears the normal progression of the song, which is not something new or interesting.

Figure 41. Case A: The center is not moved. Initial geometry of the space is preserved

Case A, the sequence is the original one:

Eb:7 Eb:7 Gb:maj Ab:maj | Eb:7 Eb:7 Gb:maj Ab:maj | Eb:7 Eb:7 Gb:maj Ab:maj

When the user moves the center a little bit, he/she will get some alterations. For instance, in Case B, the user moves it just on the x-axis, a little bit to the right. The chord sequence is changed, but there are no drastic repetitions. This case is the one that users find more interesting than the others. However, they also would like to continue to interact, move further in different axes, come back etc. That is one of the reasons that this range is quite hard to find, because the space is constantly changes according to the place of the center.

Figure 42. Case B: The center is slightly moved just on x-axis. Initial geometry of the space is changed.

Case B, the sequence is slightly altered:

Ab:maj Eb:7 Gb:maj Eb:7 | Gb:maj Ab:maj Gb:maj Eb:7 | Eb:7 Ab:maj Eb:7 Eb:7

Figure 43. Case C: The center is moved more than Case B.

Case C, the sequence is changed quite much:

Ab:maj Ab:maj Eb:7 Eb:7 | Ab:maj Gb:maj Gb:maj Gb:maj | Eb:7 Eb:7 Eb:7 Eb:7

In the last case, Case C, the center moved further away (this is a quite small amount compared to how much users moves the center in experiment runs) at the very beginning of the performance. This movement biases the light and dark blue objects, which are Gb:maj and Ab:maj, so that the user hears four Eb:7 chords at the end.

In order to determine this range, it is necessary to run task specific experiments with some rules and increased number of experiments & participants.

The sound user hear from the system is another issue. The samples are quite high quality, professional organ, acoustic guitar, clavinet, bass guitar and drum samples, but users may find a sound annoying, where I think its fine.

The tempo of the songs and the number of the chords per measure have also a significant impact. The average satisfaction level for all *Higher Ground* runs is 7.5280, for *Lyin' Eyes* is 1.8872, for *Something About You* is 13.8124. The fastest song is *Something About You* and it almost has one chord per beat. On the other hand, *Lyin' Eyes* is quite slow and the majority of the chords consist of whole notes (one note per measure). It also goes with usual pop guitar strumming, while *Something About You* is played with funky clavinet syncopations. These factors clearly affect the user satisfaction. Several participants mentioned this in different ways in the short conversations at the end of the runs.

5.2.2 User Satisfaction and the Tonal Areas

Higher Ground

	max	min
M	9	5
7	5	9

Lyin' Eyes

	max	min
M	2	6
m	7	1
7	5	7

Something About You

	max	min
M	7	8
m	7	6

Table 2. For all participants and three songs, in which area the center is when they like it most and least

This table is created to understand if there is any relation between the user satisfaction and the area of the center is on. In the *Higher Ground*, it seems like there is, however the other songs do not show any relevance to strengthen this hypothesis. The

main reason for this the number of major, minor and seventh chords are not same and they are not evenly distributed to the space. Users may like to play less abundant chords and they like them more, just because they get less of them.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

Songs successfully represented in 2D space with meaningful visualization and it perfectly gives the original model without any disturbance to the system. The system is completely appropriate for novices as it has designed to from the beginning.

The relation between users' joy and level of interaction is investigated. It has seen that there is no direct proportion between two. There is an optimal range between two, but this range also varies during the performance.

The conditions that tend to produce the cases that people like have been discovered and discussed. The effect of the center movement and its relation with the divergence from the original model have been investigated and issues have been presented in detail.

A participant mentioned that he might enjoy more, if he has more music knowledge. He agreed that it is not necessary at all to play this interface, however he posed that he do not make much sense of chord progressions without knowing some theory.

The tonal areas work and the users reported that they understood that there are more than one areas which consist different type of chords. However, they did not exactly know how many are there. They also reported that, they did not take much care of these areas, after they notice there are such areas. They focused more on playing the chords they want in the order they wish.

A few users mentioned that they did not feel like they produce tonally meaningful new music pieces. They felt like the music they produce do not completely belong to them.

6.2 Future Work

Finding the best range for maximum user satisfaction is one of the future works, which is able to produce quite a useful interface. It is necessary to run task specific experiments with some rules and increased number of experiments & participants.

The chords are one of the simplest higher order musical concepts. This whole metaphor underlying this project can be used with others, such as melodies, musical phrases, soundscapes or partition of songs (chorus, verse etc.)

This interface can be carried to online platform easily and two or more users can play it as a group. For instance, chords can be played one with a piano or guitar sound, other user can play the melody (from the idea above) and another one can play the drums as rhythmic phrases connected to each other.

References

- [1] D. Conklin, “Music Generation from Statistical Models *,” 1999.
- [2] E. Nichols, “Data-Driven Exploration of Musical Chord Sequences,” 2009.
- [3] I. Simon, “MySong : Automatic Accompaniment Generation for Vocal Melodies,” pp. 725–734, 2008.
- [4] C. Chuan and E. Chew, “A Hybrid System for Automatic Generation of Style-Specific Accompaniment.”
- [5] M. Allan and C. K. I. Williams, “Harmonising Chorales by Probabilistic Inference.”
- [6] T. de Clercq and D. Temperley, “A corpus analysis of rock harmony,” *Pop. Music*, vol. 30, no. 01, pp. 47–70, Jan. 2011.
- [7] “Fred Lerdahl, Ray Jackendoff A Generative Theory of Tonal Music 1996.pdf.” .
- [8] <https://www.h-pi.com/TPX28buy.html>
- [9] https://www.starrlabs.com/index.php?route=product/product&product_id=66
- [10] Lamb, R., & Robertson, A. (2011). Seaboard: a new piano keyboard-related interface combining discrete and continuous control. In *Proc. ICMC*.
- [11] Farbood, M., Kaufman, H., & Jennings, K. (2007). Composing with hyperscore: An intuitive interface for visualizing musical structure. In *International Computer Music Conference*.
- [12] Levin, G. (2000). *Painterly interfaces for audiovisual performance* (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology).
- [13] Wattenberg, M. (2002). Arc diagrams: Visualizing structure in strings. In *Information Visualization, 2002. INFOVIS 2002. IEEE Symposium on* (pp. 110-116). IEEE.
- [14] Bergstrom, T., Karahalios, K., & Hart, J. C. (2007, May). Isochords: visualizing structure in music. In *Proceedings of Graphics Interface 2007* (pp. 297-304). ACM.
- [15] Snyder, J., & Hearst, M. (2005, April). ImproViz: visual explorations of jazz improvisations. In *CHI'05 extended abstracts on Human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1805-1808). ACM.
- [16] G. Jacquemin, T. Coduys, and M. Ranc, “Thierry Coduys Association IanniX Matthieu Ranc,” no. Jim, pp. 9–11, 2012.

- [17] Gómez, E., & Bonada, J. (2005). Tonality visualization of polyphonic audio. In *Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference*.
- [18] D. Temperley, "What's Key for Key? The Krumhansl-Schmuckler Key-Finding Algorithm Reconsidered," *Music Percept. An Interdiscip. J.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 65–100, Oct. 1999.
- [19] Nishibori, Y., & Iwai, T. (2006, June). Tenori-on. In Proceedings of the 2006 conference on New interfaces for musical expression (pp. 172-175). IRCAM—Centre Pompidou.
- [20] Kuhara, Y., & Kobayashi, D. Kinetic Particles Synthesizer Using Multi-touch Screen Interface of Mobile Devices. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression* (pp. 136-137).
- [21] O. Bown, D. Jones, and S. Britton, "Surface as Structure : The multi-touch controller as map of musical state space," 2012.
- [22] S. Lynch, M. A. Nacenta, and S. Carpendale, "ToCoPlay : Graphical Multi-touch Interaction for Composing and Playing Music." In *Human-Computer Interaction—INTERACT 2011* (pp. 306-322). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [23] <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/hexatone-pro-idm-rhythm-generator/id324435715?mt=8>
- [24] <http://murudai.com/solar>
- [25] <http://nodebeat.com>
- [26] "Daisyphone : The Design and Impact of a Novel Environment for Remote Group Music Improvisation," In *Proceedings of the 5th conference on Designing interactive systems: processes, practices, methods, and techniques* (pp. 135–144). ACM
- [27] H. Ishii and B. Ullmer, "Tangible Bits : Towards Seamless Interfaces between People , Bits and Atoms," 1997.
- [28] M. Kaltenbrunner and M. Alonso, "The reacTable *: A Collaborative Musical Instrument," 2006.
- [29] H. Newton-dunn and J. Gib, "Block Jam : A Tangible Interface for Interactive Music," 2003.
- [30] A. Albin, M. Street, B. Blosser, O. Jan, and G. Weinberg, "Beatscape , a mixed virtual-physical environment for musical ensembles," no. June, pp. 112–115, 2011.
- [31] J. Patten and B. Recht, "Audiopad : A Tag-based Interface for Musical Performance," 2002.

- [32] Craig, A. B., Sherman, W. R., & Will, J. D. (2009). *Developing virtual reality applications: Foundations of effective design*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- [33] Schkolne, S., Ishii, H., & Schroder, P. (2004, October). Immersive design of DNA molecules with a tangible interface. In *Proceedings of the conference on Visualization'04* (pp. 227-234). IEEE Computer Society.
- [34] Brooks Jr, F. P., Ouh-Young, M., Batter, J. J., & Jerome Kilpatrick, P. (1990, September). Project GROPE Haptic displays for scientific visualization. In *ACM SIGGraph computer graphics* (Vol. 24, No. 4, pp. 177-185). ACM.
- [35] Beyls, P. (2005). A molecular collision model of musical interaction. In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Generative Art (GA 2005), Milan, AleaDesign* (pp. 375-386).
- [36] Dahl, L., & Wang, G. (2010). Sound bounce: Physical metaphors in designing mobile music performance. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME), Sydney, Australia*.
- [37] Weiss, M., Wacharamanotham, C., Voelker, S., & Borchers, J. (2011, October). FingerFlux: near-surface haptic feedback on tabletops. In *Proceedings of the 24th annual ACM symposium on User interface software and technology* (pp. 615-620). ACM.
- [38] Verplank, B., Gurevich, M., & Mathews, M. (2002, May). The Plank: designing a simple haptic controller. In *Proceedings of the 2002 conference on New interfaces for musical expression* (pp. 1-4). National University of Singapore.
- [39] Reynolds, C. (2007). Boids.
- [40] Cook, N. (1987). The perception of large-scale tonal closure. *Music perception*, 197-205.
- [41] Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990). Flow: The psychology of optimal experience. *Praha: Lidové Noviny*.
- [42] Nielsen, J. (1993). Iterative user-interface design. *Computer*, 26(11), 32-41.
- [43] Gelineck, S., & Serafin, S. (2012). Longitudinal evaluation of the integration of digital musical instruments into existing compositional work processes. *Journal of New Music Research*, 41(3), 259-276.
- [44] Luciani, A., Florens, J. L., Couroussé, D., & Cadoz, C. (2007, November). Ergotic sounds: A new way to improve playability, believability and presence of digital musical instruments. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Enactive Interfaces* (pp. 373-376).

- [45] Fallman, D., & Waterworth, J. (2005, April). Dealing with user experience and affective evaluation in hci design: A repertory grid approach. In *Workshop Paper, CHI* (pp. 2-7).
- [46] Osgood, C. E. (1957). *The measurement of meaning* (No. 47). University of Illinois press.
- [47] Hassenzahl, M., Beu, A., & Burmester, M. (2001). Engineering joy. *IEEE Software*, 18(1), 70-76.
- [48] Isbister, K., Höök, K., Sharp, M., & Laaksolahti, J. (2006, April). The sensual evaluation instrument: developing an affective evaluation tool. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human Factors in computing systems* (pp. 1163-1172). ACM.
- [49] Chateau, N., & Mersiøl, M. (2005, April). AMUSE: A tool for evaluating affective interfaces. In *CHI Workshop on Evaluating Affective Interfaces: Innovative Approaches, Portland Oregon, USA*.

Questionnaire 1:

0A - Age:

0B - Gender:

0C - Musical knowledge: none / basic / intermediate / advanced

Questionnaire 2:

Give points from 1 to 5:

System rank:

1A - The system's responses were clearly related to my performance:

1B - The system facilitated discovery of new musical combinations:

1C - The reactions of the system were predictable:

2A - I can shift the chord sequences towards the type of chords I wish, if I desire:

2B - I discovered new chord sequences:

2C - As a product of my use, I produced more interesting piece than the song itself:

3A - I liked the outcome of my performance:

3B - I have control over the system and progressions:

3C - I would perform with this system again:

3D - The system was intuitive and understandable:

Please use this space to make any comments or observations you wish about the system.

	0A	0B	0C	Ran k	1A	1B	1C	2A	2B	2C	3A	3B	3C	3D
U01	17	F	None	4	3	3	1	3	5	2	3	2	2	4
U02	62	M	Int.	3	4	3	4	3	3	2	2	3	3	4
U03	25	M	None	3	5	4	3	4	1	3	3	2	3	5
U04	26	M	Int.	4	3	5	2	4	3	2	2	3	4	4
U05	25	M	Int.	3	3	2	3	2	2	1	2	1	4	3
U06	24	F	Int.	2	3	4	2	5	3	2	3	5	3	4
U07	27	F	Basic	4	4	3	5	5	3	2	2	2	3	2
U08	28	M	Int.	4	4	4	3	5	4	2	3	3	3	4
U09	23	F	Basic	3	3	4	5	4	3	2	2	4	2	3
U10	22	M	Int.	3	4	2	4	4	2	2	2	3	2	4
U11	25	M	None	3	2	3	5	5	4	2	1	5	2	3
U12	29	M	Adv.	3	4	5	4	5	4	2	3	4	3	3
U13	24	M	Int.	4	4	3	4	4	4	2	2	4	3	4
U14	25	M	Int.	3	4	4	3	4	3	1	2	4	2	4

Table 4. Questionnaire results

	<i>Higher Ground</i>	<i>Lyin' Eyes</i>	<i>Something About You</i>
Original Song	9.318 e-202	3.845 e-119	9.382 e-159
U01	1.415 e-186	1.9417 e-124	3.910 e-141
U02	2.907 e-201	1.099 e-110	6.486 e-155
U03	1.061 e-195	6.557 e-120	1.664 e-163
U04	3.497 e-220	6.404 e-127	3.443 e-159
U05	5.593 e-202	1.109 e-106	3.905 e-155
U06	1.264 e-203	6.583 e-115	1.978 e-154
U07	4.496 e-207	1.923 e-114	2.150 e-157
U08	5.225 e-252	9.769 e-126	6.073 e-156
U09	1.464 e-203	2.233 e-118	1.954 e-148
U10	6.174 e-222	6.465 e-119	3.751 e-163
U11	3.163 e-222	3.889 e-117	7.879 e-149
U12	2.114 e-214	5.900 e-126	2.958 e-160
U13	4.207 e-206	3.419 e-127	9.908 e-155
U14	3.555 e-211	8.783 e-124	6.370 e-154

Table 5. Probabilities of original chord sequence of the chords and the generated ones by participants

<i>Higher Ground</i>	U01	U02	U03	U04	U05	U06	U07	U08	U09	U10	U11	U12	U13	U14
% M chords played in the M area	0.56	0.47	0.43	0.47	0.42	0.55	0.45	0.49	0.57	0.54	0.50	0.54	0.61	0.49
% V chords played in the V area	0.60	0.61	0.56	0.59	0.52	0.62	0.60	0.60	0.74	0.64	0.64	0.62	0.66	0.61
<i>Lyin' Eyes</i>	U01	U02	U03	U04	U05	U06	U07	U08	U09	U10	U11	U12	U13	U14
% M chords played in the M area	0.84	0.61	0.70	0.83	0.80	0.73	0.80	0.87	0.78	0.76	0.89	0.65	0.73	0.78
% m chords played in the m area	0.50	0.0	0.40	0.27	0.32	0.30	0.52	0.58	0.50	0.52	0.55	0.20	0.39	0.0
% V chords played in the V area	0.16	0.14	0.28	0.16	0.0	0.47	0.19	0.16	0.21	0.16	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.18
<i>Something About You</i>	U01	U02	U03	U04	U05	U06	U07	U08	U09	U10	U11	U12	U13	U14
% M chords played in the M area	0.85	0.0	0.78	0.82	1.0	0.88	0.74	0.93	0.79	0.84	0.84	0.98	0.87	0.74
% m chords played in the m area	0.34	0.21	0.0	0.32	0.23	0.40	0.19	0.27	0.29	0.28	0.29	0.32	0.37	0.19

Table 6. How many major, minor and dominant chords are played in major, minor and dominant areas, for each participant, for each run.